

A Modeling and Simulation-Based Study on Triple Junction Solar Cell InGaP/GaAs/Ge: The Design Parameter for High Efficient Solar Cell

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Abstract Triple-Junction Solar Cells (TJSCs) based on Indium Gallium Phosphide (InGaP), Gallium Arsenide (GaAs) and Germanium (Ge) have gained prominence for their high efficiency in converting solar energy into electricity, particularly in space and concentrated PV systems. These cells leverage a combination of three semiconductor layers to capture a broader spectrum of sunlight, thus significantly enhancing power conversion efficiency. This study aims to explore TJSCs to optimize design parameters such as material thickness, doping concentrations, and layer configurations for maximum efficiency. The study investigates the impact of thermal and radiation effects on the performance of TJSCs, focusing on key metrics like open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), Fill Factor (FF), and overall conversion efficiency. The study reveals that optimized design parameters can lead to efficiencies of up to 33.3%, with future improvements potentially reaching 48% through advanced materials like Silicon-Germanium-Tin (SiGeSn) and improved thermal management techniques. The study emphasizes the need for further exploration of long-term stability, thermal dissipation mechanisms, and enhanced radiation resistance to ensure the broader adoption of TJSCs in both terrestrial and extraterrestrial environments. Future work should focus on these challenges to enhance the durability and efficiency of solar energy systems for diverse applications.

Keywords Triple Junction Solar Cells, InGaP/GaAs/Ge, Solar Energy, Multi-Junction Solar Cells, Photovoltaic, Power Conversion.

Introduction Photovoltaic (PV) technology has become the most adopted technology in the conversion of solar energy to electric power fulfilling the endless quest for cleaner sources of energy in the world [1]. The basic working principle of photovoltaic technology is the approach of using semiconductor materials that collect solar energy and through a process of the photovoltaic effect generate electric current [2]. In the last few years, improvements in material sciences, cell engineering and production methods have fostered the development of better efficient and more robust solar cells [3]. Of all the various categories of solar cells, the multi-junction solar cells quite screamingly come to the fore with the ability to tap more solar energy thus improving efficiency further. More precisely, TJSCs are regarded as among the best in multi-junction PV technology in terms of development and efficiency [4]. They are made from three different semiconductor films each of which is matched to sunlight of distinct wavelength [5-6]. Usually, TJSCs consist of materials that include InGaP, GaAs and Ge [7]. The top layer (InGaP) captures photons with the highest energy, the middle layer (GaAs) presents eighty per cent intermediate energy photons and the lowest layer (Ge) can take lower energy photons which are not prevented by the former two layers. When layered together, TJSCs can trap much more solar energy and therefore lead to appreciable improvements in power conversion efficiency compared to a single junction solar cell [8]. This combined absorption of the solar spectrum makes the TJSCs very effective for use in areas where very high energy is needed such as in outer space or concentrated PV systems. However, due to the complexity of their design and the cost of

production, their application in terrestrial photovoltaic systems is limited [9]. Due to the complexity of multifunctional solar panels, various initiatives have been initiated and are anticipated to persist in improving the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of tandem junction solar cells (TJSCs) through advancements in materials, thermal management, and simulation techniques, thereby establishing them as a highly desirable future technology in photovoltaics [10].

Simulation of GaAs/Ge/ InGaP Triple Junction Solar Cell

The semiconductors used to construct the hetero junctions of two distinct semiconductors are required to have extremely similar lattice constants for multi-junction solar cells to be manufactured [11]. To ensure the hetero connection works as it should, semiconductors are required. This is necessary to prevent a mismatch between the two layers that are next to one another. Surface recombination is quite slow in InGaP, which is one of its distinguishing features. Multijunction solar cells use InGaP as their top cell material. An InGaP solar cell was enhanced in terms of conversion efficiency by the addition of an Indium Aluminium Phosphide (InAlP) window layer. Gallium arsenide is a remarkable semiconductor due to its straight band gap and high internal luminescence efficiency [12-14]. The maximum possible Air Mass Zero (AM0) conversion efficiency can be achieved by including a GaAs absorber in a single junction solar cell [15]. This is because the band gap energy in the AM0 spectra is almost ideal for converting the various photon energies. The band gap of Ge is 0.66 eV, which is much less than that of other elements. Its most common application is as a bottom layer in multi-junction solar cells [16]. When compared to solar cells made of silicon, those based on Ge are lighter and more efficient, making them the material of choice for space applications [17]. On the other hand, solar cells manufactured from Ge are pricier. Triple Junction solar cells consist of three layers of III-V semiconductor compounds: a Ge layer at the base, an InGaP layer at the top, and a GaAs layer in the centre [18,19]. The process involves the formation of a tunnel junction, which links the different cells. Charge carriers can go along a path with little resistance since tunnel junctions are present [20]. Ultimately, it aids in improving the efficiency of multi-junction solar cells. Figure 1 shows the design of a triple junction solar cell's internal architecture.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of InGaP/GaAs/ Ge Triple Junction solar cell [21].

The structure of lattice-matched GaInP/GaAs/Ge triple junction solar cell

The lattice-matched triple junctions solar cell is one type of solar cell that has several contemporary industrial applications on Earth and in space [22]. As of right now, it's the most powerful solar cell available in the market. On a p-type Ge substrate, this photovoltaic device was constructed. Bottom junctions between n-GaAs or p-Ge layers provide a neutral zone by enabling as-diffusion in p-type Ge substrates [23]. Subcellular carriers can thereafter be able to pass via an asymmetrical tunnel junction. Two layers of strongly doped aluminum GaInP function as barriers within the intermediate cell, which is composed of p-type and n-type GaAs. When a dot is placed on a layer, it becomes a base; when an electron dot is applied, it generates visible light by creating electron-hole pairs. The window, base, and back-surface field in the top sub-cell consists of p-doped GaInP. The window is N-doped, while the base is p-doped. Two tunnel junctions have recently formed, one connecting the upper and central sub-cells and the other between the two. To enhance the light absorption of the solar cell, an Anti-Reflection Coating (ARC) is applied after the surface's thin metal contact layers have been welded together. An investigational triple-junction solar cell is shown schematically in Figure 2 (a) and (b). Substrates made of Ge only need 140 or 80 micrometres in thickness, although p-type Ge substrates can be as

thin as a few millimetres (depending on the batch). The cell thickness is thus frequently used in place of the apparent thickness of the Ge substrate [24].

Figure 2 . (a) describes a triple junction solar cell (Ge substrate 80 µm) and (b) the composition of the lattice-matched parameter of the described junction solar cell grown on the p-type Ge substrate [24].

Modelling and simulation play a crucial role in optimizing the design parameters of TJSCs to enhance efficiency. By leveraging tools like SILVACO-ATLAS, researchers can predict and analyze the effects of material thickness, doping concentrations, and layer configurations without the need for costly and time-consuming experiments. These simulations provide insights into how small adjustments to material properties, such as lattice matching between semiconductor layers like InGaP, GaAs, and Ge, can reduce recombination losses and improve key performance metrics. Additionally, simulations help address challenges posed by thermal and radiation effects, particularly for space applications, by enabling the optimization of thermal management strategies and enhancing radiation resistance. Ultimately, modelling and simulation save time and cost by eliminating the need for multiple rounds of physical prototyping, making them essential for advancing TJSC performance in high-intensity solar applications.

Objective of study The scope of this study focuses on the detailed modelling and simulation of InGaP/GaAs/Ge TJSCs to optimize design parameters for enhanced efficiency in solar energy conversion. It encompasses the investigation of key factors such as material thickness, doping concentrations, and layer configurations to maximize the power conversion efficiency of TJSCs. The study also explores the impact of environmental conditions, including thermal and radiation effects, on solar cell performance, to analyze the physical and electrical properties of the cells. The study aims to identify design improvements that can increase efficiency from current levels to potentially higher values by integrating novel materials and advanced thermal management strategies. The findings are intended to contribute to the broader application of TJSCs in both terrestrial and extraterrestrial environments.

Review of Literature

In this section, various studies and research focused on analyzing Triple Junction Solar Cell for highly efficient solar cells are discussed:

Kharchich et al. (2023) [25] presented a fresh numerical method for developing highly efficient InGaP/GaAs tandem solar cells. The front stack of this design was an InGaP solar cell, while the rear surface field was an electric field. Large parametric simulations were carried out using the 2D SILVACO-ATLAS program, and optimization was carried out progressively via the post-processing of data outputs. At each stage of the optimization process, either a quadratic surface response model or an artificially generated neural network model was employed to fine-tune and identify the optimal solar cell configuration.

Zhang et al. (2022) [26] discovered that the harmful effects of displacement damage to solar cell materials induced by radiation were the primary perpetrators of increased cellular performance decrease. The middle subcell became the current-limiting unit when the device's usable life expired due to the severe influence of irradiation on the lifespan of the minority carriers in InGaAs. The simulated current-voltage curves and quantum efficiency spectra had a good deal of agreement with the experimental data when analogous irradiation parameters were applied.

Nakamura et al. (2022) [27] examined the degradation caused by radiation by determining the transport lifespan in the neutral and depleted areas of the InGaP and GaAs subarrays of a triple-junction solar cell consisting of InGaP, GaAs, and Ge. Using the conventional method of analysis makes it difficult to specify the degrading aspects of a carrier concentration at each place; an alternative method based on internal luminescent efficiency was proposed. The lifetime radiation damage coefficients within the faceoff circle of InGaP and GaAs subcells were two to three orders of magnitude more than those in the depletion region.

Parajuli et al. (2022) [28] investigated the fact that solar energy cells have been the subject of substantial research and were employed in both space and terrestrial applications and found that both were true. However, Multi-Junction (MJ) solar cells manufactured from III-V compounds of semiconductors could achieve an efficiency of power conversion of more than 40%, making them an attractive option for usage on Earth and beyond. It was found that triple junction sun cells had an efficiency of 33.3% at AM1.5, whereas double connection solar cells had an efficiency of 30.6%.

Bakour et al. (2022) [29] stated that the solar efficiency of a double connections InGaP/GaAs solar cell produced on a Silicon (Si) substrate was examined as a function of varying the molar concentration of the tunnelling connection and the doping intensity of the top light absorber alone. It also showed how the device's Si substrate makes it possible to employ it as a low-cost concentrator cell on the planet. All the parameters of the cell can be evaluated in detail by taking readings on its fill factors, open circuit voltage, short-circuit current, brightness, spectra density, reflectance, external quantum yield, or internal quantum efficiency.

Ding et al. (2021) [30] studied the relationship between the power required to generate Photoluminescence (PL) in a triple-junction solar cell's InGaP and GaAs subcells. Experiments have proven, and time-resolved photoluminescence measurements have validated, that larger luminescence yields result in improved luminescence coupling. In addition, a new method for determining the inherent luminous effectiveness of that and GaAs subcells was described. This method made use of luminescence coupling.

Li et al. (2020) [31] revealed that proton irradiation affected the GaAs sub-cell emitter in GaInP/GaAs/Ge quadrupled junction solar panels. The GaInP/GaAs/Ge triple-junction solar cells were only one of several typical semiconductor devices that Silvaco Altas might be used to imitate. The emitter thickness of a GaAs sub-cell can range anywhere from 0.02 μm to 0.5 μm . In quintuple solar cells, the GaAs sub-cell emitter thickness deterioration was studied of electrical and optical attributes. Triple-junction solar cells having varied GaAs sub-cell emitter thickness were simulated to degrade from 10 MeV proton irradiation.

Oh et al. (2020) [32] reported that antireflection coatings were designed and manufactured to create InGaP, GaAs, Indium Gallium Arsenide Phosphide (InGaAsP), and Indium Gallium Arsenide (InGaAs) solar cells with optimal photocurrents Antireflection Coating (ARCs). Only by meticulously developing ARCs was it feasible to double the results obtained density of cross cells, thereby unleashing the maximum potential of thin antireflection layers. This was a significant step forward in the development of thin antireflection layers.

Verma et al. (2020) [33] aimed to increase the efficiency of this energy harvesting technique by decreasing its waste heat. Although multijunction solar cells are highly efficient, they have not yet been widely adopted because of factors such as the high cost of fabrication, the low price of each watt - energy generated, etc. GaAs/ Gallium Antimonide (GaSb) dual-junction solar cells, which have a narrower bandgap, were proposed as a second option. Researchers created an illustration for a GaAs/GaSb, a double cell with a double back-surface fields layer and no ARC to make use of the planet's longer wavelengths.

Arzbin et al. (2019) [34] provided the best design for a double-junction solar cell, which included an InGaP/InGaP tunnel junction, a bottom-cell buffer layer, a pair of top-cell

Back Surface Field (BSF) layers, and a brand-new emitter layer. Open Circuit Voltage (OCV), short-circuit current density, Fill Factor (FF), and conversion efficiency were compared for the proposed cell to those of previously designed cells to determine its performance improvement via Silvaco Atlas optimization.

Yu Jeco et al. (2017) [35] presented that research into the effect of Luminescence Coupling (LC) influence on spatial nonuniformity has been conducted on the limiting cell conversion efficiency of Multi-Junction Solar Cells (MJSCs). To accomplish this, experimental laser-generated existing distribution images of the limited bottom cell have indeed been collected under various middle-to-bottom cell LC efficiencies. Maximum and minimum LC efficiencies of 8.5% and 69% were shown. Because the LC effect was not homogeneous in space, a quasi-two-dimensional simulation model was built for further analysis of the experimental data.

Wilson et al. (2016) [36] suggested Silicon-Germanium-Tin (SiGeSn), a group-IV ternary alloy, as a possible candidate material for achieving a 1.0 eV sub-cell. In intense sunlight, preliminary models of quadruple and triple connection solar cell designs revealed that this novel material combination has the potential to achieve efficiencies of 45 and 48%. There was a paper on the electrical characterization of single and triple connection devices using a 1.0 eV SiGeSn junction. Despite the alloy's early stage of development, it was demonstrated that both SiGeSn devices exhibit good external quantum efficiency performance, with a fitting minority electron diffusion layer in the junction base confined to 5 m.

Mizuno et al. (2016) [37] suggested the use of III-V-based solar cell materials to connect Pd nanoparticle arrays made from self-assembled copolymer templates. Connecting GaAs-based thin films to GaAs or Indium Phosphide (InP) based substrate (cells) was made possible by the Pd nanoparticle array, which paved the way for the creation of inter-device topologies. The improved Pd NP array's enhanced optical and electrical bonding capabilities allowed for the realization of an InGaP/GaAs top electrode as well as an InGaAsP/InGaAs bottom cell with an overall efficiency of 30.4%.

Xu et al. (2015) [38] examined the fact that the Highly Concentrated Photovoltaic/Thermal (HCPV/T) system's immediate thermal efficiency was 54%, and its instantaneous electrical efficiency was 28%. This enables the system to achieve a total efficiency of roughly 80%. Theoretical models that can calculate the temperatures of individual cells can alleviate the problem of accurately detecting system-wide temperature gradients. Also, the electrical performance parameters were evaluated under a variety of direct irradiation intensities as well as temperature conditions for the cell.

Fedoseyev et al. (2014) [39] designed a complete Three-Dimensional TCAD model of a Triple-Junction Photovoltaic (TJ PV) cell and then calibrated different physicochemical parameters to match experimental data. The 3-Dimensional Nanotechnology Computer-Aided Design (3D NanoTCAD) simulator at the Computational Fluid Dynamics Research Corporation (CFDRC) had been used to model and construct functioning triple-junction InGaP/GaAs/Ge solar cells. Detailing the model's construction by listing its materials, layer thicknesses, doping levels, or meshing procedures. This model was informed by data from Spectro lab's triple-junction cells and layer thicknesses observed at the Rochester Institute of Technology.

Meenakshi et al. (2013) [40] focused on increasing the effectiveness of the multi-junction solar cell. Design considerations such as material, layer thickness, doping concentration, texture style, or anti-reflective layer thickness are among the several factors that might impact the performance of a multi-junction solar cell. A single solar cell modelling tool, Photovoltaic Cell One-Dimensional (PC1D), was utilized to determine the efficiencies of the cells. PC1D's batch mode facilitates quick parameter optimization studies rather than iterative parameter tweaking. Each input parameter must have a range, number of values, and kind of variation (logarithmic or linear) set in batch mode.

Analysis

Comparative Analysis

Current study on triple-junction solar cells, particularly those based on InGaP/GaAs/Ge, reveals several limitations and gaps. One of the major challenges is the degradation of materials due to radiation exposure, which significantly impacts the middle sub-cell and reduces carrier lifetimes, ultimately leading to diminished performance. Despite the recognition of these effects, there is insufficient exploration of long-term degradation mechanisms, especially under varied environmental conditions, such as those encountered in space or extreme terrestrial environments. Most studies focus on short-term effects, leaving significant gaps in understanding the overall durability and lifespan of these solar cells. Another critical limitation is the lack of effective thermal management

strategies. High operating temperatures are known to degrade solar cell performance, yet there is limited research on integrating advanced thermal management solutions into triple-junction solar cell designs. Proper heat dissipation mechanisms are essential to maintaining high efficiency, especially in high-intensity solar applications. Furthermore, while significant efforts have been made to optimize individual parameters, such as material interfaces and layer thicknesses, comprehensive studies addressing the optimization of the entire cell structure for real-world applications are still lacking. Simulation models often fall short of being validated through extensive experimental data, which limits the practical application of these theoretical advancements in actual solar energy conversion systems.

Table 1 illustrates various research efforts on solar cell technology, focusing on different techniques to improve efficiency. These techniques include manufacturing MJ solar cells using III-V compounds, investigating the influence of luminescence coupling on spatial nonuniformity, developing preliminary models of quadruple and triple connection solar cell designs using SiGeSn, connecting GaAs-based thin films to GaAs or InP-based substrates using Pd nanoparticle arrays, and developing a highly concentrated photovoltaic/thermal system. The study resulted in varying levels of efficiency, with MJ solar cells achieving over 40% power conversion efficiency and triple junction solar cells reaching 33.3% efficiency. Other techniques demonstrated efficiencies ranging from 8.5% to 69% and showed potential for achieving higher efficiencies in the future.

Table 1. Comparison of Literature Review.

Authors	Technique Used	Efficiency
Parajuli et al. (2022) [28]	MJ solar cells are manufactured from III-V compounds of semiconductors.	MJ solar cells achieved over 40% power conversion efficiency; triple junction solar cells had 33.3% efficiency.
Yu Jeco et al. (2017) [35]	LC influence on spatial nonuniformity using experimental laser-generated images.	LC efficiencies ranged from 8.5% to 69%; spatial nonuniformity influenced cell conversion efficiency.
Wilson et al. (2016) [36]	Preliminary models of quadruple and triple connection solar cell designs using SiGeSn	SiGeSn devices showed good external quantum efficiency, with the potential to achieve efficiencies of 45-48%
Mizuno et al. (2016) [37]	Connecting GaAs-based thin films to GaAs or InP-based substrates using Pd nanoparticle arrays	Pd nanoparticle array enabled the realization of a solar cell with an efficiency of 30.4%
Xu et al. (2015) [38]	Highly Concentrated Photovoltaic/Thermal (HCPV/T) system with theoretical models	HCPV/T system demonstrated a total efficiency potential of approximately 80%, with 54% thermal efficiency and 28% electrical efficiency.

Result and Discussion

The study emphasizes various successful strategies for enhancing the efficiency of TJSCs, particularly those based on InGaP/GaAs/Ge. A key finding is the importance of optimizing material selection and design parameters, including material layer thickness and doping concentrations, which are crucial in improving power conversion efficiency. Multi-junction configurations have demonstrated the potential to reach high efficiencies, with triple-junction cells achieving over 33%. Thermal management and radiation effects are critical factors, as radiation exposure significantly impacts the middle subcell, leading to reduced carrier lifetimes and diminished performance. Advanced simulation techniques, such as those utilizing SILVACO-ATLAS, allow for fine-tuning of these design parameters, providing insights into how material and layer configurations can be optimized for maximum efficiency. The optimization of emitter thickness and managing thermal degradation is also essential, particularly in high-intensity solar applications. Luminescence Coupling (LC) has been identified as another crucial factor, influencing spatial uniformity and significantly enhancing cell performance when optimized, with LC efficiencies ranging from 8.5% to 69%. Additionally, integrating advanced thermal management solutions and further exploring innovative materials, such as SiGeSn, could further improve the overall efficiency of TJSCs, with potential efficiencies as high as 48% demonstrated in simulation models. These findings underscore the importance of continued research

into material innovation, thermal management, and radiation resistance, which are essential for the development of next-generation solar energy systems, particularly for applications in space and high-intensity terrestrial environments. Future research should focus on the long-term stability of these materials, enhanced thermal dissipation mechanisms, and advanced simulation methods to optimize solar cell designs for varying environmental conditions.

Conclusion

TJSCs based on InGaP/GaAs/Ge represent a cutting-edge advancement in photovoltaic technology, capable of efficiently converting a wide spectrum of sunlight into electrical energy. By optimizing design parameters such as material thickness, doping concentrations, and layer configurations, these cells have shown significant potential for achieving high efficiency in solar energy conversion. This study highlights the significant potential of optimized design parameters in TJSCs for achieving high efficiency, with reported efficiencies of up to 33.3% under standard conditions and the potential for further improvement to 48%. Key optimizations include material thickness, doping concentrations, and effective thermal management, which are critical for enhancing overall performance, especially in high-intensity applications such as space exploration. Emerging technologies, such as advanced simulation tools like SILVACO-ATLAS and innovative materials like SiGeSn, offer promising avenues for further enhancing photovoltaic cell performance, particularly in addressing challenges such as radiation damage and thermal degradation. Future research should focus on improving long-term stability and developing advanced heat dissipation mechanisms, ensuring the durability and wider adoption of TJSCs in both terrestrial and extraterrestrial applications.

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